

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Milestones

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ETrP	ELIXIR Training Platform
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Executive Summary

The ELIXIR Training SPLASH project seeks to establish a collaborative, centralized, and user-friendly digital resource designed to showcase the diverse products and resources developed by the ELIXIR Training Platform (ETrP) over the years. Currently, these resources are dispersed across various online channels, making it challenging to grasp the comprehensive scope of existing and ongoing training projects.

The primary objective of the SPLASH project is to enhance accessibility and ensure the long-term impact of these training resources by creating a digital "one-stop-shop". This platform will serve trainers, trainees, training developers and providers, funders, and other ELIXIR Platforms and Communities. It aims to raise awareness and recognition of often overlooked or misrepresented aspects of training and addresses a critical gap observed in grant-funded projects, where subject experts typically conduct training without the involvement of educational experts, resulting in unsustainable training. To remedy this, the ELIXIR Training Platform encourages early engagement with ELIXIR Communities and projects prior and during proposal development to establish collaborative sustainable training strategies.

Central to SPLASH is the Training Lifecycle, a unifying process that integrates all training components with a focus on promoting best practices in training. The Training lifecycle provides an overarching view of the various products and services offered by the Training Platform, fostering collaboration among stakeholders. Key projects within the Training Lifecycle include:

- ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer programme
- Learning Paths project
- FAIR training project
- Links to tools like TeSS, Training Metrics Database
- EeLP eLearning Platform
- Certification process for ELIXIR courses and training materials

The uniqueness of the Training Lifecycle lies in its role as the first process to consolidate all ETrP products in a centralized, accessible format. The long-term ambition of the SPLASH project is to become a recognised platform for best practices in training within the life sciences and beyond, ultimately setting a new standard for Training. By centralizing these resources, the SPLASH project aims to ensure that training is not only accessible but also conducted with the highest standards of educational expertise, thereby fostering sustainable and impactful training programs across the life sciences field.

Outcomes and Impacts of the milestone

Milestone *M3.1 Consolidate the key components of the ELIXIR Training lifecycle by discussions with Training Excos and Training Coordinators* is part of the SPLASH project. The output of this milestone was finalised and the Training lifecycle stages are now displayed on the SPLASH website¹.

Figure 1: The Training Life Cycle¹

This milestone was achieved after several discussions and workshops with the Training Platform and Training Coordinators. Workshops included:

- SPLASH kickoff meeting (22 August 2023)
- SPLASH Training Lifecycle brainstorming meeting (6 October 2023)
- Biohackathon Europe 2023 Project: SPLASH Project (20 October -3 November 2023)
- Training Life Cycle Workshop 1 (22 April 2024)
- Training Life Cycle Workshop 2 (3 May 2024)

Further workshops are planned to develop the narrative of each stage, working towards *D3.1 A homogeneous narrative of the training lifecycle steps, connected to the various documents/SOPs/Best practices*.

¹ <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/>